

COGNITIVE MATRIX FORMAT OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH AN ANTHROPONYMIC COMPONENT IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Human's knowledge about anthroponyms has an integrative nature and this can be represented in cognitive matrix format consisting of core and periphery parts [Bochkareva, 2012; 5]. In this case, cognitive contexts which are integrally related with each other are distinguished on the basis of encyclopaedic information about anthroponyms. In consideration of anthroponyms participated in the component of phraseological units in the English and Uzbek languages, ANTHROPONYM constitute the core of cognitive matrix and such cognitive contexts as HISTORY, RELIGION, MYTHOLOGY, FOLKLORE, LITERATURE, PEOPLE compose its periphery.

1) In the cognitive context HISTORY of the concept ANTHROPONYM encyclopaedic information about outstanding features, life and activity of historical people who left remarkable influence in the past are reflected in the phraseological units with an anthroponymic component. For example, in English *A Potemkin village; Joe Miller; Hobson's choice; Draconian law; Prince Albert; Father Abraham*, and in Uzbek *Aflotun miya; Amir Temurdan qolgan; Devonayi Mashrab; Asfandiyor xon bo'ldi, og'zi-burnim qon bo'ldi; Padarkush Abdullatif*, and so on. It is evident that the phraseological unit *Jack Ketch* in English embodies a historical episode connected with an English executioner Jack Ketch who served under the reign of King Charles II and James I in England in human's conceptual picture of the world. In consideration of his occupation as an executioner and his cruelty, a negative connotation related with hangman and murderer is formed in human's mind. The phraseological unit *Mahmudning qadami yetgan joyda o't o'smas* in Uzbek creates an image of a fierce bloodthirsty, tyrannical invader Mahmud Gaznaviy in human's conceptual world picture. According to historical literature, he slaughtered the people of Central Asia in blood and brought destruction to the nation with his military actions at the beginning of the 11th century. In view of such

negative behaviour, this phraseological unit formulates a concept representing those who always unleash their anger do not bring goodness and blessing.

2) In the cognitive context RELIGION of the concept ANTHROPONYM encyclopaedic information about outstanding features, life and activity of religious images mentioned in religious statements are reflected in the phraseological units with an anthroponymic component. For instance, in English *As patient as Job; A doubting Thomas; A Daniel come to judgement; A man of Belial; Benjamin of the family*, and in Uzbek *Xizr nazar qilgan; Isoning alamini Musodan olmoq; Odam Atodan qolgan; Muhammad payg'ambar madadkor bo'lsin*, and so on. The phraseological unit *A doubting Thomas* in English is derived from an apostle Thomas depicted in Bible. According to this source, Thomas does not believe prophet Jesus' resurrection despite his death under brutal crucifixion and his burial in cave. However, he believes that he has been resurrected after having embarked on journey to meet him. Considering his distrust in resurrection of the prophet without evidence, this phraseological unit activates an associative meaning related with a sceptical man who does not believe something without witnessing evidence in human's mind. The majority of phraseological units with a religious anthroponymic component in English are emerged from Bible and they certainly reflect significant concepts about Christian culture formed under the influence of Christianity [Fedosova & Kutyeva, 2021; 90]. The prophet Khizr in the component of phraseological unit *Xizr nazar qilgan* related with stories about prophets in Uzbek is mentioned in Islamic legends, according to which, he is interpreted as the supporter of sailors in the sea, eager to help those in need when called with special prayers, blesser of farmers and peasants. On account of such qualities, this phraseological unit is associated with those who has an illuminous future and blissful life in modern linguistics.

3) In the cognitive context MYTHOLOGY of the concept ANTHROPONYM encyclopaedic information about outstanding features, life and activity of heroes mentioned in ancient Greek and Roman mythological stories are reflected in the phraseological units with an anthroponymic component. For example, in English, *Achilles' heel; Cassandra warnings; In the arms of Morpheus; Between Scylla and Charybdis; Penelope's web; Castor and Pollux; As rich as Croesus*, and so on. Such examples are not found in the Uzbek language. From a cognitive viewpoint, the phraseological unit *A Pandora's box* in English is considered as a cognitive model reflecting a story connected with ancient Greek mythology in human's mind. According to myth, a woman called Pandora opened a box out of curiosity, as a result of which she caused all kinds of trouble [Kun, 2005; 45]. In consideration of such behaviour, this phraseological unit denotes a circumstance generating many perplexing troubles in modern linguistics.

4) In the cognitive context FOLKLORE of the concept ANTHROPONYM encyclopaedic information about outstanding features, life and activity of heroes glorified in masterpieces of folklore are reflected in the phraseological units with an anthroponymic component. For instance, in English *Tom Thumb; Mother Bunch; Fortunatus' purse*, and in Uzbek *Qora Botir; Oti yomon – Oypora; Ayamajuz olti kun, qahr aylasa qattiq kun; Rustami doston bo'lmoq*, and so on. The phraseological unit with an anthroponymic component *Tom Thumb* in English incarnates a diminutive boy depicted in English folktale "Tom Thumb" in human's mind. In view of his size no bigger than a thumb, the phrase is used to describe those who are shorter in height in modern linguistics. The phraseological unit with an anthroponymic component *Qora Botir* in Uzbek directly reflects a character Qora Botir described in epic poem "Farhod and Shirin",

famous among Turkic and Persian literary circle, in human's mind. Taking into account his attempt to obstruct and get in the way of the relationship between couple Farhod and Shirin, this phraseological unit is used to describe those who interfere a certain situation or impede somebody else's plans.

5) In the cognitive context LITERATURE of the concept ANTHROPONYM encyclopaedic information about outstanding features, life and activity of personages written in the works by eminent authors are reflected in the phraseological units with an anthroponymic component. For example, in English *Billy Bunter; Jekyll and Hyde; Colonel Blimp; Cordelia's gift; Hamlet without the Prince; A Peter Pan*, and in Uzbek *Tata-tat, usta Nadirmat; Layli va Majnun; Majnun bo'lib qolmoq*. In English the interpretation of the phraseological unit *A Sherlock Holmes* necessitates to be extensively aware of English literature. Sherlock Holmes, a favourite protagonist of works by an English detective novelist Arthur Conan Doyle, is a man of high deductive reasoning. Because of his ability to resolve criminal mysteries by deduction, this phraseological unit conceptualizes a policeman who conducts criminal affairs with the help of his deductive thought. In Uzbek the phraseological unit *Majnun bo'lib qolmoq*, considered as the product of literary works, embodies a famous Turkic and Persian epic poem "Layli and Majnun" in human's conceptual world picture. According to the epic poem, Majnun is extolled as the archetype of deep perfection for love. On account of such perfection of love, this phraseological unit activates a man who possess a sincere and deep affection in human's mind.

6) In the cognitive context PEOPLE of the concept ANTHROPONYM encyclopaedic information about outstanding features, life and activity of common national people are reflected in the phraseological units with an anthroponymic component. They mainly exemplify and embody those who have certain kind of outstanding features. In particular, in English *A good Jack makes a good Jill; Every Tom, Dick and Harry*, and in Uzbek *Alining alamini Validan olmoq; Ishni Ismat qiladi, lofni Toshmat uradi; Mulla Mirashir, qilmishiga yarashir; Hazil – hazil, hazilni tushunmagan kal Fozil*, and so on. The anthroponyms in such phraseological units in English as *A good Jack makes a good Jill; Every Jack shall have his Jill; All shall be well, Jack shall have Jill; Jack and Jill* typify a couple dwelling in English society. The anthroponyms in the component of such phraseological units in Uzbek as *Mulla Mirashir, puliga yarashir; Mulla Mirashir, qilmishiga yarashir; Mulla Mirashir, topganin bizga tashir; Ashir topganin tashir* are used ironically and humorously by Uzbek people with intention to embody the general image of those who complain about worthlessness and poor quality of something after purchase or those who get punished because of their wrongdoings, or even those who share what they possess despite being in need.

In conclusion, with assistance of the cognitive model of cognitive matrix format of knowledge about anthroponyms in the component of phraseological unit in the English and Uzbek languages, a clear image and precise regulation of such knowledge can be obtained. Based on the encyclopaedic information about anthroponyms in the phraseological units, the cognitive matrix format of them consists of such cognitive contexts as HISTORY, RELIGION, MYTHOLOGY, FOLKLORE, LITERATURE and PEOPLE.

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